

Reshaping the Block Patterns for Circular Economy - A Review Study

Leela Mantri & Smriti Agarwal*

¹Mody University, School of Design, Lakshmanagarh (SOD)

Abstract:

The Fashion Industry plays a key role in generating designs to meet the growing demand of consumers. Block pattern is a key feature to amalgamate the pattern with design elements (colors, prints, fabric, and textures) creating mesmerizing designs to take fashion to new horizons. Blocking the pattern with different mediums can make the possibility of designing for different occasions. Application and Experimentation with Different color combinations, prints, fabrics, textures, and Decorative details will add to the aesthetics of the wearer. Color Blocking is the most adaptable and takes the creditability of this original concept. This can serve the purpose of the design industry to enrich design concepts with the Circular economy. Pattern makers and Designers' effective coordination can serve the interest of society and withstand the challenges prevailing in the industry. Pattern makers as Technical Engineers can create endless possibilities for design endeavors. Most notable is the designs evolve with the major Pattern-making principles and accentuate the wearer's desire to retain the fit involved in the garment.

Keywords: Block Patterns, Circular economy, Colour blocking, Pattern makers, Reshaping

*Corresponding Author:

Prof. Smriti Agarwal
School of Fashion Design
Mody University,
Sikar Road, Laxmanagarh, Narodara Rural,
Siker – 332 311 Raj
E-mail: dr.smritiagarwal@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Block patterns are foundation patterns used to develop varied styles of tops and dresses. The urge for something new has been existing for ages and meeting the demand of people has been a major concern of designers. They are accentuated for developing varied styles of patterns through different design concepts. Blocking the patterns through colors, prints, and textures can meet the growing demands of the Fashion Industry. The prevailing economic situations have centred designers on creating designs that are economical and sustainable. The concept of Redesigning bodice blocks with colors, prints, and textures can serve the requirement of designers to create innumerable designs for the Industry. Revival of past concepts is the need for a circular economy. Thought to create the patterns with usage of colors, prints, and textures in generating new designs can supplement the concept of remake and reuse in Fashion.

Inspirations and themes can be part of this design process. An application or Experimentation with colors, prints, and textures can create unique designs for different categories of wear. Dart manipulations and style lines can be supportive to retain the fit of the bodice or dress. Blocking the patterns or creating designs with prints and colors can develop styles for casual, resort, and leisure wear. Application of Textures and ornamentation with embroidery in these blocks can generate designs for evening and luxury wear. The utility of leftover pieces at production labs is more prominent in reshaping blocks for Sustainable Fashion.

1.1 Color Blocking & Fashion

Color Blocking in Fashion is the skill of wearing different solid structures of colors as a silhouette to create bold and mesmerizing looks. The concept applies to Fashion accompaniments as well [1].

Color Blocking was initiated with the idea of experimenting with colors in silhouettes to create fascinating looks. It became a source for design explorations. Origin is from the artwork of Dutch painter, Piet Mondrian. Geometry was an inspiration to develop styles with the use of primary colors as a base from the color wheel. It included the composition of contradictory colors in an outfit to emphasize the dark and compact colors and become an eye-catching detail [3]. It resembled an abstract form of art and was quite simple to develop designs. As per norms, certain principles have to be followed in the planning of colors to balance and create harmony in designs. Color theories and color wheel play a vital role in the planning of colors.

Figure 1: Collection of Yves Saint Laurent Mondrian [1].

A pattern is a basic model of a silhouette or an accessory to develop the outcome. Color blocking allows the utilization of the scraps of fabrics that remained as waste and unutilized. It became a utility for designers and pattern makers to regenerate various styles at a minimal cost. Pattern makers technically consider these as style lines for dart manipulation. It is related to TR pattern cutting by Shingo Sato a truly inspirational Japanese artisan [2,3].

This color-blocking strategy or approach can bring advances in designing for Sustainable Fashion. Designers and Fashion Brands will be able to generate fashion goods in large quantities and make them more affordable and accessible. Easy patterns with simple blocks for garments and accessories can be supportive in this process. It generates a source of employment for the majority of people and benefits society.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 The Working process for CB

Experimentation done with the inspiration of Geometric design, from floor designs, at pattern making lab is illustrated below Designs can be preplanned, inspired by the desired source, or could be experimented with to create unique styles.

Figure (2a). Drafting pattern No.1

(2b). Geometric design inspiration for drafting pattern (a) Made you Look 7 Cut Design Black-7X8. [4]

(2c). Geometric design: 3Triangulation Series 2022 #1 Mona Mark [5].

In the process of planning, can take desired silhouettes like tops, skirts, pants, sleeves, and dresses.

Drafting Pattern 1 “Fig. 2a” Illustrates trace the basic bodice pattern as shown. Asymmetric designs need an open lay of pattern for design application. Division of Spaces can be uniform with planning or can be random to create abstract designs or set geometric patterns. “Fig.2b” and “Fig. 2c” represent a source of inspiration to form geometric designs. Design choice can be based on the category of wear, age group, and overall look desired. Plot the pattern with the design of choice. Label it. Symbolize for Identification of all the segregations. Identification points assist in matching the pattern and completing the sewing accurately. Sewing skills and expertise are essential in such design elevations. Any mismatch can distort the shape of the silhouette and fit involved in it. The study states that this experiment can be conducted in two ways. The former method is to place the front and back bodice together at the side seam and chart the divisions. Symbolize the fabric segments and cut the pieces with a seam allowance of 1cm, match and sew. Notches are essential at pivot points and if any curved areas. Press the seams open at the inside part after joining the two pieces together. After accomplishing the desired pattern, the finishing of other prominent areas like the Neckline, shoulder joint, side seams, hem finishing with facings, and fasteners at the center back of choice can enhance the garment.

As similar to color blocking in a pattern color could be replaced with prints. Small prints are more suitable for block divisions as a balanced look could be achieved.

Solid colors could be paired with prints and textures. Stripes can also accentuate the complete look as the effect of the grain line is more visual.

2.2 Different Techniques of CB

2.2.1 CB Technique with Solid Colors (“Fig. 3”, “Fig. 4a,4b”, “Fig. 5”)

Solid colors create a set of harmony with its application. Color wheel with a set of colors, color schemes, and color theories guide in the selection of colors. Monotonous and contrasting effects could be achieved based on their combinations.

Fabrics applied have the same weight. Opaqueness and Transparency are two vital tools to create an unusual impact. Design planning can be structured or soft as per the needs of the user.

(3)

(4a)

(4b)

(5)

Figure (3) &(5): final design outcome of Solid color fabrics

(4a), (4b): Front design and back design top with stiff organza transparent fabric

(6a)

(6b)

Figure (6): Drafting No.2: Initial Working step process of Figure No. 3 design

with Muslin stitched 3d pattern

Figure (6) Drafting No.2 illustrates the design plan for “Fig. 3”. This developed design has continuity in design flow from front to back. We can introduce style lines passing through the apex point and thereafter as desired. It has been worked by using a 3d block. This developed design has continuity in design flow from front to back. Fabric leftovers have been utilized to cut pattern pieces and join them to form a design.

(7a)

(7b)

Figure (7a): Front Draft (7b): Back Draft

Drafting No.3 : Working step Process of design Figure (4a &4b) are illustrated on the paper pattern

Drafting No.3 Illustrates the block design plan initiated to construct the “Fig.4” design. Design planning has been done on the front bodice and back bodice paper pattern separately. These are represented as style lines of pattern making and pass through the bust points to retain the fit and get accustomed to the stitching process easily. Templates are cut after labelling them and with indication marks to guide during the construction to match the seam lines. They are cut as individual pieces and scraps of fabrics are used to lay and cut them. A seam allowance of 1cm is taken on all sides of the fabric directly.

Figure (8a): Step 1

Figure (8b): Step 2

Figure (8c): Step 3 & 4

Figure (8a), (8b),(8c) Drafting No.4 : Working Process of Figure 5 is illustrated

Drafting no.4 illustrates the working process of Image 6. Design planning has been done on paper as per the dimensions of the bodice and initiated in the fabric. Scraps of fabric have been joined and cloth has

2.2.2 CB with Solid colors and prints (“Fig. 9a”, “Fig.9b”, “Fig.9c”)

This combination accentuates the fabric composition of solid-colored fabric and printed fabric. The visual impact of this combination creates attention to the pattern and gives a balanced effect to the silhouette.

(9a)

(9b)

(9c)

(10a)

(10b)

(10c)

Figure (9a), (9b), (9c): Final design outcome of a combination of Solid Color & Printed fabrics

Figure (10a) , (10b), (10c) are Drafting No.5, 6,7 of design (9a) ,(9b) (9c) respectively

2.2.3 CB technique with two printed fabrics

Coordinating two prints in the same silhouette is quite challenging. The combination of small and large print breaks the monotony and adds to fabric depth. Prints with similar sizes give a well-coordinated look. Mixing of bold and small prints creates a very strong visual effect and balances the contrast.

(11a , 11b)

(12)

(13)

Figure 11a, 11b : Final design outcome with printed fabrics

Figure 12 : Drafting No. 8 of design 12 worked on front bodice paper pattern

Figure 13 : Drafting No. 9 of design 13 worked on front bodice paper pattern

(14a)

(14b)

Figure 14a,14b : Front & back top final outcome with pleats decorative detail

(15a)

(15b)

Figure 15a, 15b : Drafting No.10 of design 14a &14b Front & back pattern respectively

**** Self Conducted experimentation on the blocking concept with the assistance of students at Hamstech College of Creative Education, Hyderabad 2023.**

Materials used for Pattern Drawings were soft lightweight color papers, marker pens, L-scale, Pattern master curve, and French curve, Gateway sheets. Experimentation at the lab was done with cotton-blended solid color fabrics ,printedfabrics & stiff dyed organza fabric for sewing convenience.

2.3 CB -2D versus CB-3D

Pattern-making offers innumerable ways to complete the pattern as per the design choice and convenience of the field worker (sewers). Any application does not hamper the fit and look of the silhouette. Fabric pieces could be assembled accurately to obtain the desired look and accentuate the body curve to create an overall impact on the wearer. Tops can be paired with any bottom of choice to complete the outfit look in monotone colors or complementary colors as per design and utility.

Designers have used geometric shapes in color blocking with 3D look to create desired effect as shown below:

(16)

Fig: No. 26 [6]

There are innumerable design inspirations to plan the divisions in a garment. Close-fitted, Semi-fitted, and Flared silhouettes can be worked with the color-blocking concept using the different methods and techniques discussed above.

Table 1: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF 2D AND 3D BLOCKS

S. No.	Reshaping 3d blocks	Reshaping 2d blocks
1.	Dress form or a person is essential to visualize and plot the pattern.	The pattern can be plotted on the 2d pattern of a garment.
2.	Stitched garments can be used for design plans and the same as templates for cutting the pattern pieces.	Paper patterns can be used for design plan & and cutting.
3.	Further alterations in the garment are not possible.	An alteration option is available.
4.	Fabric consumption for laying is more due to style continuity.	Looks more adaptable with the use of the fabric consumption
5.	Dart closures are not required. Greater scope for design innovations	Darts have to be closed or eliminated from the patterns to complete the design innovations.

2.3.1 A comparative study in the application of the concept is done in 3 ways:

Firstly, Working with 3D patterns has continuity and flow in front and back design without regular seams, style lines are sewn together to complete the look of the outfit as per design.

Secondly working with a 2D pattern that enables divisions which can give a scope of alteration for the fit required as regular seams exist.

Thirdly and lastly traditional technique was used. The fabric was created from leftover scraps and thereafter pattern placed gave freedom to set design within the frame only.

These divisions in a block converting darts into style lines retain the fit of the garment. Identification marks guide to match the seams during the assembling of these pieces. Joining and matching of seams.

The traditional System of joining scrap pieces and forming a cloth is quite universal and has its own do's and don'ts.

3. Results and Discussion

Designs Working with CB had a great impact as designs were found unique and endless possibilities for ascertaining them. The pattern retained its original fit after construction and was the most liked by the designers and end users. The idea was to experiment directly on tops as it would establish the basis to implement on various

types of garments and fashion accompaniments. The concept was found to be more sustainable as it utilized the scrap pieces and supported in development of designs for different fashion products. The first and second drafting techniques (Ref: Drafting 2&3) are considered the most suitable which had negligible or minimal wastage. There was a great metamorphosis with the application of color blocking in designs and it truly represented the original creation of the creator. As experimentation with solid colors was inclined towards casual wear designs, the combination of printed fabrics with plain-colored fabrics developed for formal wear. Texture application or G.C. detailing techniques (eg. Tucks, pleats, gathers, ruffles, smocking, or embellishments) can be accentuated for evening wear. Students were fascinated with mesmerizing designs obtained through innovations and it was quite easy to develop the patterns for the user needs. Fitted silhouettes can opt for block patterns to generate designs with CB. Digital patterns were applied with the idea of augmenting the design usage for both mass and High Fashion industries. Designers have always been in the limelight for their creations in Industry. Creditability for pattern makers is more in as they are the backbone for design development.

4. Conclusion

Blocking of patterns has laid endless possibilities for Design innovations. Every design can be unique in its aspect. This technique stands ideal for Sustainable Fashion. Generates a source of employment for the industry to collect the scraps of materials and make productive use of them for Design innovations. The Role of Pattern Making and Construction is crucial for the growth of Industry as it supports designers to build their designs and explore new creations. Designs developed by blocking the pattern have vast scope as they meet the needs of all the wear categories. Fashion is an art and Pattern Making techniques are a medium to innovate in the field of Design Education.

Acknowledgment

** Garment Samples showcased are the outcome of Self-conducted experimentation on the blocking concept with the assistance of students at Hamstech College of Creative Education, Hyderabad 2023, and Mody University Pattern Making lab team 2023.

** Drafting of patterns for the analysis of color blocking was self-designed to experiment at the Lab Mody University Science and Technology.

References:

- [1] <https://www.bing.com/images/search>.
- [2] Sato, S. [2011]. Transformational Reconstruction [Vol. 2]
- [3] Amany El-Dosuky, A. (2023). Using Transformational reconstruction (T.R) as a technique for developing creativity in fashion design education. *International Design Journal (Print)*, 13[4], 203. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ijdj.2023.305340>
- [4] MADE YOU LOOK 7 CUT DESIGN-BLACK -7X8. [n.d.]. WWW.FLOR.COM.
- [5] TRIANGULATION SERIES 2022, #1 MONA MARK. [n.d.]
- [6] <https://i.pinimg.com/originals/7e/8d/aa/7e8daa8f2fcdc79f75e3ff01c811e1d9.jpg>
- [7] "A Brief History of Color-blocking". Bliss by Design. Retrieved 18 October 2015
- [8] Aldrich, Winifred. 1997, Metric Pattern Cutting. Blackwell Science Ltd U.K.
- [9] Duffer, Ellen [23 March 2012]. "Origin of the Trend: Color Blocking"
- [10] "Fashion Inspired by Art: Piet Mondrian's Color-blocking". Retrieved 18 October 2015
- [11] Michi, T. N. *Pattern Magic* [1st ed.]
- [12] "Origin of the Trend: Color Blocking". Archived from the original on 24 October 2015. Retrieved 18 October 2015.
- [13] "Rules of Colour Blocking". DNA. Retrieved 18 October 2015
- [14] *Shapes of fabric*. (2020) (Internet) <https://www.theshapesoffabric.com/author/adwirawen/>
- [15] www.byrdie.com/what-does-color-blocking-mean-in-fashion - 5187279